

Greenhouse evaluation of synthetic pyrethroids for tungro (RTV) control

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We tested several synthetic pyrethroids (see table) for their ability to prevent RTV. Cypermethrin 1 and cypermethrin 2 at 0.05% concentration, and deltamethrin at 0.01% effectively prevented RTV infection (see table). With deltamethrin, even 0.005% was effective. All the insecticides tested caused 100% vector mortality 1 d after treatment (DAT). Cypermethrin 1, cypermethrin 2, and deltamethrin caused 100% vector mortality at both dilutions at 5 DAT.

Studies on the mechanism of prevention of infection by these insecticides are

in progress. Preliminary results with cypermethrin indicate that it has powerful

fumigant and repellent actions, in addition to contact toxicity. □

Effect of synthetic pyrethroids on RTV prevention and vector *Nephotettix virescens* mortality, Cuttack, India.

Insecticide	Concentration (%)	% prevention ^a of infection		Vector mortality (%) ^b	
		1 DAT	5 DAT	1 DAT	5 DAT
Deltamethrin	0.005	93 c	62 c	100	100
	0.01	100 d	100 d	100	100
Fenvalerate	0.01	46 a	38 b	100	55
	0.05	95 c	91 d	100	100
FMC54800	0.01	49 a	11 a	100	45
	0.05	93 c	38 b	100	85
Cypermethrin 1	0.01	85 bc	56 bc	100	100
	0.05	100 d	100 d	100	100
Cypermethrin 2	0.01	71 d	47 bc	100	100
	0.05	100 d	100 d	100	100

^a % prevention = $\frac{\% \text{ infected plants in control} - \% \text{ infected plants in treatment}}{\% \text{ infected plants in control}} \times 100$.

Values followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at P = 0.05. ^b Values adjusted with Abbott's formula.

The relative evaluation system - a quantitative technique for disease assessment of rice breeding materials in the field

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Many resistance mechanisms of rice plants against various diseases are manifested not only in a qualitative way (absence of visible symptoms) but also in a quantitative manner (less amount of disease at a given time). Quantification of disease is complicated, laborious, and highly variable, particularly when a large number of breeding materials must be evaluated in the field. The *relative evaluation system* (RES) was developed to overcome those shortcomings.

RES recognizes that human eyesight is relatively good at comparison (equal to, less than, or more than) but poor in quantification, even with the help of pictorial guides. Each grade on the RES scale (Table 1) is based on the relative amount of disease instead of a predetermined disease level. The procedure (Table 2) is simple and can be easily followed by inexperienced observers. The key is to form and retain a mental image of disease intensity for grade 5 and for the

standard entry. For better use of the system, a set of reference entries, which consist of several known materials with different ranges of quantitative resistance to particular disease, should be included. Use of an extremely susceptible cultivar for comparison should, however, be avoided.

RES can be used in assessing several foliar diseases of rice plants, including slow blasting, and panicle diseases such as grain discoloration or panicle B1 if the flowering period of test materials is synchronized. RES is particularly suitable

for breeders because their main interest is not the absolute amount of damage but the relative performance of plants or lines as compared to reference materials or local checks. □

Table 1. Scale for the Relative Evaluation System.

Grade	Description
0	Careful observation of a plant or plot reveals no lesions or infected plants.
1	Rapid observation does not detect lesions or infected plants, but careful observation detects a few lesions or infected plants.
3	Rapid observation easily detects a few lesions or infected plants.
5	Disease level is between grade 3 and 7. Distribution of lesions or infected plants is fairly uniform.
7	Disease level is clearly less than that of the standard entry.
9	Disease level is similar to that of the standard entry.

Table 2. Procedure for the Relative Evaluation System.

Step	Procedure
1	Carefully observe all the entries. If there are several entries showing disease levels higher than grade 3, proceed to step 2.
2	Select one entry with a higher level of disease at the time of evaluation, and assign grade 9. This entry is called the standard entry at the time of evaluation. This may vary from evaluation to evaluation.
3	Form a mental image of the standard entry, which serves as a guide for grade 9.
4	Evaluate individual entries comparing the relative level of disease with those of adjacent entries. Intergrades 2, 4, 6, and 8 can be used when necessary.
5	For actual quantification of disease, evaluate 4 or 5 randomly selected entries for each grade using a pictorial guide or any available method to compute the value for each grade using either arithmetic average or regression.
6	Transform all the grades into quantitative terms for further analysis.